

MECHANISMS OF TRAINING FEMALE CADETS IN BELT WRESTLING AND PROMOTING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Annotation. In modern society, the role of the young physically active generation with a strong life and civic position is increasing. The martial arts classes of girls in the conditions of the university have a positive impact on the formation and development of their personality. Sports activities are closely related to the process of sports education, they are able to satisfy the need for movement and form the desire for a healthy lifestyle. Many girls want to engage in power sports and martial arts. Girls should be selected for sports sections based on the presented selection system. It is necessary to take into account the level of health, physical fitness, characteristics of the female body. The article outlines the main conceptual approaches to the process of physical education of girls in the university using the means of freestyle wrestling. The optimal ratio of volume and intensity of training loads was revealed. The technique of selection of girls in the section of free-style wrestling at the university is given.

Key words: freestyle wrestling, physical education at the university, sports selection, sports training, motivation.

Аннотация. В современном обществе возрастает роль молодого физически активного поколения с сильной жизненной и гражданской позицией. Занятия девушек боевыми искусствами в условиях вуза положительно влияют на формирование и развитие их личности. Занятия спортом тесно связаны с процессом спортивного воспитания, они способны удовлетворить потребность в движении и сформировать стремление к здоровому образу жизни. Многие девушки хотят заниматься силовыми видами спорта и единоборствами. Девочек следует отбирать в спортивные секции на основе представленной системы отбора. Необходимо учитывать уровень здоровья, физическую подготовку, особенности женского организма. В статье изложены основные концептуальные подходы к процессу физического воспитания девушек в вузе средствами вольной борьбы. Выявлено оптимальное соотношение объема и интенсивности тренировочных нагрузок. Приведена методика отбора девушек в секцию вольной борьбы в вузе.

Ключевые слова: вольная борьба, физическое воспитание в вузе, спортивный отбор, спортивная подготовка, мотивация.

Introduction. In Uzbek wrestling, the qualities inherent in the spirit and original qualities of our people, courage and bravery, tolerance, nobility towards the opponent and the philosophy of humanity have been embodied.

The physical culture of students of higher educational institutions is one of the main components of the formation of professional competence of qualified personnel and differs significantly from physical education lessons in secondary school. Teaching physical education at the university forms and reinforces healthy habits among young people.

As Ibn Sina said, a healthy mind is in a healthy body. Currently, the head of our country pays great attention to the development of all types of women's sports at the level of modern requirements.

The body of women differs from that of men in a number of morphological and functional features. This situation does not affect the physical activity they perform, therefore, it is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of the female body when women engage in sports.

It depends on how to organize and conduct sports training to train young athletes and improve their skills. When organizing sports training, it is necessary to study the personal characteristics of female athletes. This plays a very important role in filling the groups with new and less qualified athletes during training.

However, in universities, as well as in educational institutions of other levels, the problem of motor activity motivation is relevant, some students have a lack of desire and interest in attending physical education classes. Therefore, it is necessary to use differentiated forms of organizing classes, taking into account the interests of those involved.

Classes in such groups contribute to the comprehensive development of physical qualities. In addition, the technique and tactics of freestyle wrestling are being mastered and improved, skills of successful use in various conditions of competitive activity are being formed.

Elective courses provide for taking into account the interests and inclinations of those involved, provide for an independent and conscious choice of a sports section. Sportization is one of the ways to form a positive motivation for physical culture and sports.

Sportization of the process of physical education ensures the satisfaction of the need for physical activity, instills a commitment not only to a healthy lifestyle, but also to a sporty lifestyle.

Students learn the joy of victories, learn to analyze and accept defeats, observe the rules of fair play.

One of the conditions for admission to sports training is the health status of the participants. First of all, it is necessary to pass a medical examination before being allowed to participate in sports activities. As a result, it will be determined whether the applicant can play sports and which type of sports can be beneficial for health. It is necessary to take into account the general physical fitness and sports experience of athletes when forming and filling groups and when making a training plan. Because, compared to beginners, professional athletes perform complex exercises quickly and endure physical exercises for a long time.

When drawing up a training plan, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the working women's organism, study, living and professional conditions.

Therefore, the coach and medical staff, about the women's body. Those who have certain knowledge should be well acquainted with the profession, study and living conditions. Living conditions can negatively and positively affect the nervous system, sleep quality, complete rest after work and sports. Taking these conditions into account, the coach should help the athlete as much as possible to improve his life.

It should be noted that our women's national team is not achieving good results at the world level. The first reason for this is that Uzbek wrestling has become more difficult to popularize among women compared to men, and wrestling is only a men's sport is considered. The second reason is the involvement of coaches who train with men before women's wrestling.

Practice shows that all coaches of women's training are men and in many places boys and girls participate in training together. The third reason is that the training methods, structure and loading standards of male wrestlers are fundamentally different from those of women. Attracting women to sports is one of the most pressing issues today.

One of the traditional homes of our people is wrestling. Of course, every nation has formed many competitions and contests during its history. Many sports competitions have been invented to test people's dexterity, agility, strength and willpower and the history of these competitions is as old and continuous as the history of mankind.

Sports of Uzbekistan is an integral part of our national culture. It is one of the important tools for raising young people in a high moral spirit and strengthening their health. The peoples living in our country have created various types of physical exercises and national competitions for centuries, which in turn had a significant positive effect on the physical and spiritual education of young people.

Wrestling is one of the oldest sports and has a very interesting and bright history. For many thousands of years, ancient man has passed a difficult path from instinctive attack and defense actions to coordinated actions close to modern fighting methods.

It was a characteristic of that time that wrestling was equated to art along with other physical exercises. Great representatives of that time - scientists, poets, statesmen, generals - were engaged in wrestling.

Uzbek wrestling was born in ancient times, and it is reflected in a large number of historical monuments.

During the archaeological excavations conducted in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan, ancient paintings depicting the methods of fighting, which include the methods of peaceful settlement of disputes, as well as the capture of the enemy, were found. It is worth mentioning that before the competitions, exercises were performed, including throws, jumps and demonstration of strength. They served as a means of warming up the opponents before the competition. Wrestlers grabbed each other's leather belts or different parts of their upper clothes and started fighting. When performing the method of throwing the opponent to the ground, great attention is paid to the work of the legs and the method of striking.

In the peoples living in the territory of Uzbekistan, the competition continued until the first throw. These competitions were held to the sound of national music and the winner of the competition was highly respected by the people.

Belt wrestling differs from other sports due to the many and varied technical movements of the athlete.

The classification, systematization and terminology of wrestling techniques were developed to regulate the technical actions of the wrestler and to create an opportunity for communication between specialists in this field.

The principles of training belt wrestlers are the general-theoretical principles of training wrestlers and teaching methods.

The following principles are implemented in the training of belt wrestlers.

1. Pedagogical (didactic) principles (the principle of awareness and activity, the principle of demonstrability, the principle of regularity and sequence, the principle of comprehensibility and individualization).

2. Principles of improvement of sports skills (principle of strength and variability of skills, principle of compatibility and principle of joint conduct in a directed manner).

3. Principles of sports training (the principle of achieving the unity of general and special physical training, the principle of repetition and continuity of the training process, the principle of gradation, the principle of gradually increasing training loads).

The physical training of a belt wrestler is one of the important components of sports training and is a process aimed at developing physical qualities - strength, endurance, flexibility, agility and quickness.

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